

Posture Monitoring of Patients in Radiotherapy Scenarios Based on Stacked Grayscale 3-Channel Images

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Abstract: Purpose: Incorrect patient positioning during radiotherapy can significantly impact treatment efficacy and pose potential risks. This study aims to develop a model that can rapidly and effectively monitor the patient's postures during radiotherapy sessions using real-time video. Methods: The neural network utilized in this research employed a two-stream architecture, consisting of spatial and temporal streams. For the spatial stream, RGB frames from the videos were directly used as input. In the temporal stream, representative frames were extracted from

the video to construct stacked grayscale 3-channel images (SG3I) frames. This approach enabled capturing motion information through a large-scale dataset pre-trained 2D convolutional neural network (CNN), eliminating the need for computationally expensive optical flow calculations. Additionally, an improved lightweight network architecture was employed. The model was trained and tested using volunteer videos collected from a radiotherapy center in a hospital.

Results: The results demonstrated that the proposed model outperforms existing methods in terms of detection accuracy while achieving higher efficiency in frame generation.

Conclusion: In this study, we introduced a cost-effective and highly accurate method for recognizing patient's postures during radiotherapy. This approach could be readily deployed in any radiotherapy facility, ensuring treatment precision and patient safety.

Keywords: Posture recognition, Radiotherapy, Spatial-temporal CNN, Computer vision

Categories: I.2, I.4, J.3, L.3

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1 Introduction

Among all causes of death, malignant tumors have emerged as a highly perilous cause of mortality [Rahman et al., 2020]. With the continuous advancement of medical technology, the application of radiotherapy in tumor treatment has become increasingly widespread, leading to an extension of the survival period for cancer patients. However, incorrect positioning during radiotherapy can impact the effectiveness of treatment and even worsen the patient's health condition. Despite radiotherapists advising patients to avoid making any abnormal movements prior to the therapy, it is not always feasible to ensure that patients maintain a completely normal posture due to individual variations. Furthermore, abnormal posture may be a signal of discomfort to the patient, implying the likelihood of subsequent movements, and in certain cases, even posing a significant threat to their safety. Additionally, prolonged radiation treatment duration can result in reduced attention levels of radiotherapists, potentially introducing risks during manual monitoring processes.

Currently, commercially available radiotherapy systems [Bellala et al., 2023] provide higher treatment accuracy by focusing primarily on position correction and compensating for minor displacements of the radiation target caused by bodily movements such as breathing. However, they do not effectively alert or address more significant abnormal posture. Moreover, these commercial radiotherapy systems are expensive and complex to deploy, making them inaccessible, particularly in underdeveloped countries or regions.

With the advent of the 5G era, the number of Internet of Things (IoT) devices has grown exponentially [Qi et al., 2017, Tripathi et al., 2016]. Human pose recognition has already found widespread applications in areas such as safe driving, fall prevention, and posture detection [Gupta et al., 2015, Mai et al., 2023, Gupta et al., 2020]. However, there has been limited research focusing on intelligent monitoring systems within radiotherapy rooms. Computer vision-based intelligent monitoring systems offer a significant advantage as they do not require expensive purchases or complex deployments of commercial radiotherapy systems. By simply installing cameras within the therapy room, these systems can automatically detect patient poses, allowing for plug-and-play deployment in radiotherapy rooms under various equipment conditions.

1.1 Related Work

Pose recognition is a key research direction in computer graphics, with applications spanning human-computer interaction, virtual reality, and beyond. This field can be broadly classified into two categories based on the recognition techniques employed. The first approach relies on data captured by specialized sensor devices, such as smart bracelets or glasses, to recognize body posture. However, these devices can be costly and uncomfortable for users, limiting their widespread adoption. For instance, Miranda et al. proposed a method that describes human posture using the angles between skeletal joints, which is then classified using multi-level support vector machines (SVMs) and decision forests [Miranda et al., 2014]. Lei et al. studied the use of RGB-D cameras for fine-grained recognition of kitchen activities. This method is set to combine shape and appearance to locate hands and track changes in object motion to identify objects and their functions [Lei et al., 2012]. Jeong et al. proposed a method for classifying walking activities using an eight-foot pressure sensor embedded in smart shoes [Jeong et al., 2017]. These methods have high requirements for sensors and cannot fully achieve real-time recognition outdoors. The second approach utilizes imaging devices to capture visual data of the human body and employs computer vision techniques to analyze body posture. Traditional methods in this category focus on extracting features from RGB images to describe visual and 2D posture information. With the advancement of deep learning technologies, image-based pose recognition methods have increasingly become the mainstream approach. The integration of deep learning frameworks, such as Convolutional Neural Networks (CNN) and Graph Convolutional Networks (GCN), has significantly enhanced the accuracy of human joint detection and action recognition. Moreover, dynamic pose recognition has evolved to incorporate time-series analysis techniques like Long Short-Term Memory Networks (LSTM) and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), enabling more effective capture of temporal variations in complex actions. This combination of spatial and temporal processing has considerably improved the robustness and performance of pose recognition systems. In reference [Joe et al., 2015], CNN will obtain a global description. Due to the sharing of parameters in the time series, both feature aggregation and LSTM architecture remain unchanged as functions of video length. In 2020, Ji et al. proposed an action genome to enhance the correlation of motion time features and capture changes in the pairwise relationships between objects during action [Ji et al., 2020]. Ullah et al. proposed a Conflux LSTM network to recognize actions from multi view cameras [Ullah et al., 2021].

In recent years, there has been a high expectation for the effectiveness of deep neural networks in video action recognition, following their tremendous success in static image tasks. However, unlike many existing pre-trained 2D convolutional neural networks (CNNs), there is a lack of 3D CNNs pre-trained on large-scale video datasets. Consequently, training a 3D CNN from scratch using specific domain video datasets becomes necessary, demanding a substantial amount of training videos and computational resources. Additionally, the generalization capability of such models may not be as strong as pre-trained ones. For instance, Song et al. proposed an improved method for violence detection in videos based on a 3D CNN [Song et al., 2019]. They designed a sampling method with keyframes as segmentation nodes, and the sampled data required processing through a 3D CNN.

In order to utilize pre-trained 2D CNNs, researchers have proposed a method for video action detection based on static images. For instance, Nunez et al. introduced a fall detection approach for non-fall scenarios by extracting motion features from optical flow images [Adrián et al., 2017] and employing the VGG-16 network for fall detection. Simonyan et al. proposed a two-stream convolutional neural network (CNN) model [Simonyan et al., 2014], which consists of spatial and temporal networks. The spatial stream takes representative frames selected from video recordings as inputs, while the temporal stream uses optical flow frames obtained from consecutive video frames. The two-stream CNN then combines the features from both streams. The LightAnomalyNet achieves detection efficiency through two principal components, and it does not require large computational load or memory space. Therefore, we have opted for the two-stream convolutional neural network for training, using a LightAnomalyNet.

However, it should be noted the use of optical flow frames in the two-stream CNN results in significant computational load and memory space requirements, leading to higher recognition latency. This limitation poses challenges to the practical application of the two-stream CNN, especially in the context of patient safety during radiotherapy processes, where high latency is unacceptable. Therefore, it is necessary to reduce the computational complexity of the temporal stream CNN before implementing the two-stream CNN in an intelligent monitoring system for radiotherapy rooms.

Reference	Data used	Feature/Model
Miranda et al.	skeletons	SVM
Lei et al.	RGB-D	Wearable cameras, sensors
Jeong et al.	Pressure signals	SVM, sensors
Joe et al.	RGB	CNN, LSTM
Ji et al.	RGB	3D-CNN
Ullah et al.	RGB	Conflux LSTMs
Song et al.	RGB	Key frames sampling, 3D-CNN
Adrián et al.	RGB, optical flow	2D-CNN
Simonyan et al.	RGB, optical flow	Two-stream 2D-CNN

Table 1: Summary of posture recognition studies

1.2 Contribution

In this work, we aim to combine the advantages of advanced methods to improve detection accuracy while minimizing resource load, specifically addressing the real-time pose detection problem in radiotherapy processes. The main contributions of this study are as follows:

- 1) We propose a network that achieves optimal performance with a relatively shallow network depth by leveraging advanced pre-trained convolutional neural networks and integrating spatial and temporal information.

2) For the temporal stream, we employ an advanced motion representation method that accurately identifies behaviors using motion features, eliminating the need for expensive optical flow.

3) We introduce an intelligent model for real-time monitoring of patient poses within radiotherapy rooms, with the potential for quick and cost-effective deployment. This model aims to enhance the quality of radiotherapy by preventing potentially dangerous movements caused by abnormal poses, thereby ensuring patient safety.

Experiments conducted on a volunteer pose video dataset collected from a radiotherapy room in a hospital demonstrate that our approach effectively extracts motion information from videos. A series of ablation experiments confirms our selection of different network architectures, achieving high accuracy while reducing computational complexity, with an accuracy rate of 97.82%.

1.3 Paper Outline

The details of the proposed steps for patient posture recognition in radiotherapy scenarios, based on Stacked Grayscale 3-Channel Images, are presented in Section 2. This section includes the methods for generating temporal and spatial flows, visualization technique, as well as the description of the lightweight network architecture. In Section 3, we conducted experiments and evaluations of our approach, including ablation studies and comparisons with other methods. Subsequently, in Section 4, we discuss the limitations and future work of this study. Finally, a summary of our work is provided in Section 5.

2 Method

Our method aims to detect non-standard patient postures accurately and quickly from real-time videos during radiotherapy. To achieve high precision detection, the proposed approach utilizes appearance information in the spatial flow and complex motion information in the temporal flow to detect patient movements. To improve detection efficiency, the method has been improved in two aspects. Firstly, compared to methods that require significant computational and memory resources, such as using optical flow frames in a two-stream network [10] or directly feeding videos into a 3D CNN [Varol et al., 2018], we employ a computationally less expensive motion feature modeling approach called Stacked Grayscale 3-Channel Images (SG3I) [Kim et al., 2020]. Due to the stable nature of radiotherapy scenarios, SG3Is effectively capture motion details. Secondly, instead of using highly complex neural network architectures for training and classification, we utilize an improved lightweight network structure. This structure is simpler, minimizes computational load, and provides high accuracy when trained on RGB and SG3I images. An overview of the lightweight network framework is shown in Figure 1. The following section will introduce in detail the process of generating SG3I images and using the lightweight CNN to classify them as standard or non-standard postures.

Figure 1: The overall architecture of the action recognition

2.1 SG3Is Formation for Temporal Stream

SG3I is an image composed of three frames extracted from a captured video in chronological order. Each frame is assigned to one of the RGB channels of the SG3I image. Specifically, as shown in Figure 2, SG3I is obtained by converting the extracted three frames into grayscale images using only the luminance component, and then assigning these three frames to the RGB channels of SG3I. If the three grayscale images have the same pixel value at a particular coordinate, the synthesized SG3I will display a colorless grayscale at that location. Conversely, it will display a color representing the luminance offset of the three frames. If there is a change in the RGB values at a certain pixel position in the temporal sequence, it may indicate the presence of object movement. Therefore, the colored regions in SG3I can provide information about moving objects, and the shape of these regions contains motion feature information.

Figure 2: Flow chart of SG3I formation

Figure 3: Sample of SG3I images

It is important to note that the selection of appropriate frames to create SG3I is crucial. On one hand, it is necessary to choose frames uniformly, ensuring that the time intervals between frames are not too long to avoid capturing noisy motion. On the other hand, the intervals should not be too short, as it would render this method meaningless. To strike a balance, we adopt a technique similar to [Kim et al., 2020]. Specifically, this technique divides the video into numerous sub-videos of configurable sizes, and then generates an SG3I for each sub-video. This technique ensures that the selected frames represent the entire video. Sample SG3Is from the dataset used in this study are depicted in Figure 3.

2.2 RGB Images Formation for Spatial Stream

In order to enhance the accurate recognition of spatial attributes of objects by the model, it is crucial to carefully choose a representative frame from the video. To facilitate the selection process and ensure optimal frame inclusion with the object, a technique resembling the temporal stream frames is employed. The video clip undergoes segmentation into multiple sub-clips, enabling the selection of a representative frame for each sub-clip. It should be noted that SG3Is and RGB images need to be correlated to establish a cohesive interpretation for the CNN. Consequently, the approach maintains a record of the frames and pixels containing motion information that were selected during the creation of inputs for the temporal stream. Specifically, while constructing the RGB image input, it selects one of the previously chosen three frames to generate an SG3I. This methodology allows for the acquisition of multiple RGB images from the video footage, which are then employed to fine-tune the spatial stream of the CNN.

2.3 Explainable deep learning using Grad-CAM

In order to make deep learning more readable and interpretable, we used Gradient Weighted Class Activation Mapping (Grad-CAM) technology [Panwar et al., 2020], which provides an interpretable view of the deep learning model. Unlike other methods, Grad-CAM is applicable to a variety of CNN model architectures.

2.4 Lightweight CNN Architecture

Xception [Chollet, 2019] is an improved model introduced after Inception v3 [Szegedy et al., 2016], which is based on the Inception [He et al., 2016] architecture. It primarily utilizes depthwise separable convolutions to replace the multi-dimensional convolutional kernel feature response operations in Inception v3. Additionally, it incorporates skip connections inspired by ResNet [Szegedy et al., 2015]. The Xception model can be divided into three streams: the entry flow, middle flow, and exit flow. It consists of a total of 14 blocks, with 4 blocks in the entry flow, 8 blocks in the middle flow, and 2 blocks in the exit flow. Each block is composed of a residual convolutional network combined with a SeparableConv2D layer. The most common combination of layers within a block is Relu, SeparableConv2D, and Batch Normalization. In the entry and exit flows, the sequence of layers is primarily SeparableConv2D, Batch Normalization, and Relu. In the middle flow, the sequence is mainly Relu, SeparableConv2D, and Batch Normalization.

This work focuses on improving the combination of layers in the middle flow to minimize network parameters while maintaining accuracy. For convenience, let's abbreviate the combination of Relu, SeparableConv2D, and Batch Normalization as RSB. The middle flow consists of a repeating three-layer RSB structure, which involves multiple convolutional layers. While this is suitable for complex scene classification, it may be more appropriate to reduce the number of convolutional layers for radiotherapy scenarios in this work. Therefore, we experimented with different network structures in the middle flow. Specifically, by varying the number of RSBs in the middle flow, we created seven different lightweight network structures, referred to as LXception. The performance of each network structure was evaluated. Due to their high accuracy and fewer parameters, we ultimately selected a three-layer RSB middle flow, as shown in Figure 4, which was repeated three times and used in both spatial and temporal streams. More details about the experimental results are provided in Section 3.3.

Figure 4: Structure of proposed Lightweight Xception network

3 Experiment

We conducted extensive experiments to evaluate the proposed method's ability to monitor whether the patient's posture is standard in a radiotherapy environment. All experiments were implemented using TensorFlow 2.0 in Python. The main steps of the proposed algorithm are as follows:

Algorithm 1: Posture detection for radiotherapy patients.

```

Input :  $\delta \rightarrow$  datasets
         $\mu \rightarrow$  learning rate
        BS  $\rightarrow$  batch size
         $\epsilon \rightarrow$  number of epochs
Output:  $\omega \rightarrow$  CNN weights
begin;
1. Dataset processing.
2. Selecting Train, Test and Validate data split.
3. Calculating class weights for train sets.
4. basemodel – Lxception3(weights, imagenet)
5. Initialize the hyperparameters:  $\mu$ , BS,  $\epsilon$ 
6. Train the CNN model and store the output weight ( $\omega$ ).
for  $\epsilon = 1$  to callback do
    Forward propagation and compute the binary
    cross-entropy loss.
    Backpropagation and update adam optimizer.
end

```

3.1 Dataset

To validate the proposed method, we communicated with the patients with the help of technicians in hospital. After obtaining the patient's consent, we used multiple cameras in the treatment room to capture 65 video samples from different angles. These videos included both standard actions, such as crossing hands above the head, and non-standard actions that could potentially lead to injury, such as raising hands, not crossing hands, and spreading them apart. Figure 5 shows examples of different actions. We then used the method described in Section 2.1 to obtain RGB images and SG3Is. Additionally, data augmentation is a commonly used technique to address class imbalance and expand the dataset. When the model sees slightly varied versions of the input continuously, it has the potential to learn robust data patterns more quickly. To increase the amount of data, the initially obtained SG3Is were randomly cropped around the center, horizontally flipped, and resized to a size of 299×299 . Subsequently, the dataset was configured with an 8:1:1 ratio, resulting in 5,689 frame samples in the training set and 711 frame samples in both the validation and test sets.

Figure 5: Different movement on our self-collected dataset. The last two movements represent standard postures, while the rest depict non-standard postures.

3.2 Implementation Details

During the training process, we analyzed the performance of two different optimizers: SGD and Adam. For both optimizers, we tested various learning rates, momentum, weight decay, and Nesterov acceleration parameters. If the loss didn't decrease after 10 epochs of iteration, we reduced the learning rate by 1/10. Among the tested configurations, the Adam optimizer performed best with a learning rate of 0.001, beta1 value of 0.9, beta2 value of 0.999, and epsilon value of 10^{-8} , without enabling AMSgrad. During the testing phase, the same configuration was consistently applied to all datasets. The processor used is the Intel(R) Core(TM) i5-13500H 2.60 GHz, with a memory size of 16.0 GB. The graphics card is the NVIDIA RTX 4050.

Hypermeters	Values
Batch Size	Samples
Train Validate Test Split ratio	8:1:1
Optimizer	Adam
Input size	299*299 pixels
Dropout	0.5

Table 2: Hyper-parameters values used in the experiments

3.3 Ablation Studies

In Section 2.3, we created seven different lightweight network structures by varying the number of repeated blocks in the Middle flow. This was done to explore the balance between efficiency and accuracy. Under the same conditions, all seven network structures, including the original baseline structure, were trained, and the accuracy and parameter count were recorded for each dataset. The results are summarized in Table 3. The LXception3 structure, composed of three repetitions of three-layer RSB (Relu, SeparableConv2D, and Batch Normalization), achieved the best accuracy with a relatively shallow network structure compared to other configurations. Therefore, this

structure was used simultaneously in both the spatial and temporal streams in our subsequent experiments. Henceforth, in the remaining parts of this section, Xception refers to the lightweight structure of LXception3.

Methods	Accuracy	Parameters
Xception	0.9706	20,865,578
LXception7	0.9719	19,247,234
LXception6	0.9733	17,628,890
LXception5	0.9747	16,010,546
LXception4	0.9754	14,392,202
LXception3	0.9782	12,773,858
LXception2	0.9749	11,155,514
LXception1	0.9735	9,537,170

Table 3: Comparison of the accuracy and parameter counts of different LXception structures

Additionally, experiments were conducted to investigate the roles of each stream in the proposed two-stream architecture. The results are presented in Table 4. From the table, it can be observed that the spatial stream CNN plays a primary role in monitoring posture performance, while the temporal stream complements and enhances the overall performance when fused together.

	Spatial	Temporal	Fused Two Stream
Recall	0.9884	0.9800	0.9851
FP Rate	0.0686	0.0574	0.0434
Precision	0.9735	0.9760	0.9861
Accuracy	0.9724	0.9690	0.9782

Table 4: Comparison of Experimental Results Using Temporal Flow Alone, Spatial Flow Alone, and a Combination of Both

3.4 Performance Evaluation

The performance of the proposed model was evaluated on the test set of the dataset described in Section 3.1. Figure 6 presents the confusion matrix, illustrating the training results for the two categories: standard radiotherapy postures and non-standard radiotherapy postures. The model achieved an accuracy of 95.38% for classifying standard postures and 98.61% for non-standard postures. It is worth noting that in this dataset, the percentage of standard postures misclassified as non-standard was slightly higher than the percentage of non-standard postures misclassified as standard. However, this is considered satisfactory since for a radiotherapy posture detection system that concerns patient safety, a slightly higher false positive rate is more acceptable than a high false negative rate.

Furthermore, the ROC curve and AUC value shown in Figure 7 provide a deeper understanding of the model's true positive rate and false positive rate. The model achieved an AUC value of 0.98 on the dataset, indicating its strong performance.

Figure 6: Confusion matrix showing the results of the model on the test set

Figure 7: ROC curve depicting the results of the model on the test set

The training accuracy, validation accuracy, training loss, and validation loss graphs are shown in the Figure 8. It can be seen that as the number of epochs increases, the loss gradually decreases and the accuracy gradually improves. Furthermore, there is no

indication of overfitting or underfitting. To better visualize the patient's posture, we also applied a visualization technique to the image using Grad-CAM. The results are shown in Figure 9, where it is clear that our neural network places more focus on the patient's torso.

Figure 8: Training loss, validation loss, training accuracy, validation accuracy

Figure 9: Visualize results using Grad CAM

Additionally, one of the other objectives of this study is to reduce the computational complexity required for temporal flow. The method proposed in this paper achieves this by utilizing SG3Is instead of optical flow frames during the generation of input frames in a pre-trained 2D CNN. Therefore, it is necessary to experimentally verify the effectiveness of SG3Is in improving the efficiency of frame generation. We compared the frame rates of the optical flow method [Brox et al., 2004], the dynamic image method [Bilen et al., 2016], and the proposed SG3Is method for frame generation. The results are presented in Table 5. It is important to note that for the optical flow method, we used a GPU to obtain optical flow, while the other two methods were tested solely

on a CPU. As shown in the table, despite utilizing a GPU for obtaining optical flow, its speed is still inferior to the other methods. Furthermore, the SG3I method demonstrates significantly higher performance in generating input frames compared to the other two methods.

Methods	FPS
Optical Flow [Brox et al., 2004]	16.2
Dynamic Image [Bilen et al., 2016]	178.3
SG3I	795.6

Table 5: Execution times in frames per second (FPS) for generating input frames for the temporal-stream CNN among optical flow, dynamic images, and the proposed SG3I methods.

Furthermore, we also conducted tests on the inference speed of the lightweight CNN. For the entire two-stream process, the inference frame rate reached 47.4fps, which enables the method to fully meet the real-time pose monitoring requirements in radiotherapy scenarios. When a camera captures an image, the model generates SG3I by considering this image as the last frame of a temporal sequence of three frames. This process achieves a speed of up to 700fps and then feeds the generated SG3I into the lightweight CNN for inference. Since the typical frame rate of the camera's video capture is 30fps, the overall inference speed of the model exceeds the frame rate of the camera's captured footage.

3.5 Accuracy Comparison with other methods

To further evaluate the effectiveness of our method in recognizing standardized patient postures in radiotherapy scenarios, we compared them with competitive methods with similar objectives. In this work, we reproduced four recent methods, and the experimental results on our dataset are presented in Table 6.

1) [Simonyan et al., 2014] proposed a two-stream convolutional neural network architecture incorporating spatial and temporal networks, with RGB and optical flow frames serving as inputs to the spatial stream network and the temporal stream network respectively.

2) [Brezovský et al., 2018] focused on the research of motion action recognition based on 3D convolutional neural networks, and achieved a high accuracy rate in the experiments.

3) [Li et al., 2019] followed the two-stream network and designed an end-to-end behavioral feature learning method using a novel 3D convolutional network (ConvNets) and pyramid pooling layer.

4) [Yao et al., 2019] proposed a two-stream convolutional neural network that combines joint information with skeletal information for action recognition. As shown in Table 6, our method achieved a detection accuracy of 97.82%, outperforming the competitive methods.

5) [Jiang et al., 2023] developed a patient pose recognition system using ResNet-18's deep learning to detect incorrect patient poses.

Methods	AUC%	Accuracy%
[Simonyan et al., 2014]	83	83.2
[Brezovský et al., 2018]	78	76.53
[Li et al., 2019]	85	84.7
[Yao et al., 2019]	93	93.24
[Jiang et al., 2023]	96.3	95.6
Ours	98	97.82

Table 6: Comparison of classification accuracy with other methods

4 Discussion

In this work, we proposed a method based on two-stream CNNs for monitoring whether patient's postures were standardized in radiotherapy scenarios. This method utilized an improved pre-trained 2D CNN for both spatial and temporal streams. To achieve high detection performance while allowing for lower computational costs, we inputted RGB image frames and SG3Is as the spatial and temporal streams, respectively, to the CNN. When combined with lightweight CNN architectures, SG3Is provide an effective alternative to classical motion representation methods such as optical flow and dynamic images. Consequently, our method exhibits superior recognition performance and computational efficiency compared to existing approaches.

Although our method achieves higher accuracy and efficiency compared to other motion detection methods for patient posture monitoring in radiotherapy environments, using a lightweight network architecture, there are still some limitations. Firstly, even with a 98.61% detection rate for abnormal postures, there is still room for improvement when it comes to patient safety in radiotherapy environments. Unless we achieve a 100% detection rate, there is still a need for further enhancements. Secondly, this work is preliminary research and focuses more on the technical feasibility. After detecting abnormal postures, the system can send alerts to patients and notify radiotherapists immediately, but it cannot control the operation of the radiotherapy equipment or perform position compensation. More clinical studies are needed before formal application.

5 Conclusions

This work presented a method using two-stream CNNs to monitor whether patient's postures were canonical in radiotherapy. By leveraging improved pre-trained 2D CNNs with RGB image frames and SG3Is as inputs, the method achieved superior recognition performance and computational efficiency compared to existing approaches, accurately detecting abnormal postures with 98.61% accuracy.

6 Future Work

In future work, we will continue to expand the dataset, including both the number of samples and the variety of postures. We will utilize more advanced neural networks to

train intelligent radiotherapy room safety monitoring models with higher accuracy, robustness, and efficiency. We will also explore estimating abnormal positions in 3D space, assessing the level of danger for abnormalities, and predicting possible further patient movements. Additionally, we plan to integrate our method with radiotherapy systems and investigate methods for tracking the position of the radiation target using low-cost computer vision techniques. This will enable us to perform position compensation for minor posture errors and halt radiation delivery in case of severe danger, while maintaining an economically friendly and plug-and-play advantage.

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